

On the Performance of the Free-Access Tree Algorithm with MPR, SIC, and Single-Slot Memory

Čedomir Stefanović*, Dejan Vukobratović†, Marko Beko ‡§

†Department of Electronic Systems, Aalborg University, Frederikskaj 12, Copenhagen, 2450, Denmark

†Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

‡Instituto de Telecomunicações, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa

§COPELABS, Universidade Lusófona de Humanidades e Tecnologias, Lisbon, Portugal

Abstract—In this paper, we investigate performance of a random access scheme that exploits binary-tree algorithm (BTA) with the free access. We assume a scenario where the receiver is capable to perform both multi-packet reception (MPR) and successive interference cancellation (SIC), where for the purpose of the latter only the last received and undecoded signal can be stored. We distinguish between two variants of the algorithm, where in the first the SIC can be triggered by a decoding event but also executed blindly among yet undecoded slots, while in the second the receiver can only execute the SIC after the decoding event. We analytically derive the maximum stable throughput (MST) of the scheme assuming Poisson arrivals. The evaluation shows that the scheme is able of achieving a favorable performance in comparison to the scenarios when only either MPR or SIC with single-slot memory is used, making it a suitable candidate for an access solution in applications that are characterized with a massive number of users and sporadic traffic arrivals. We also compare the performance of the scheme with the best performing BTA scheme that also exploits K -MPR and SIC and does not have memory limitations, showing that the relative difference in the MST's of the two schemes diminishes with K .

Index Terms—random access, tree algorithm, maximum stable throughput, successive interference cancellation, multi-packet reception

I. INTRODUCTION

During the past decade, wireless Internet of Things (IoT) technologies expanded their range from short-range indoor connectivity to wide-area outdoor connectivity via cellular networks [1]. Covering potentially billions of sensing devices, novel methodologies to design and operate massive IoT networks are needed. Massive IoT service is characterized with sporadic, short and asymmetric (predominantly uplink) data transmissions from a massive number of users. The critical design problem is how to enable reliable and timely access to IoT devices while taking into account stochastic and intermittent nature of the traffic arrivals in these setups. Present solutions are typically based on random access protocols, which are exploited in all cellular access technologies, either for a connection establishment, e.g., in the case of LTE/NB-IoT [2], or immediate data delivery, like in Wireless M-BUS [3]. However, random access methods built upon the classical ALOHA protocol will represent a bottleneck in the long term, thus novel enhanced random access solutions are needed [4].

Among traditional random access schemes, tree algorithms (TA) can attain higher stable throughputs than the slotted ALOHA-based schemes [5]. Moreover, their performance can be significantly increased by exploiting advanced techniques at the physical layer that can effectively deal with collisions among packets of the contending users. Specifically, the use of multipacket reception (MPR) implies that the collisions are not destructive by default, but they may be utilized to improve the maximum stable throughput (MST) [6]–[8]. Another beneficial technique is the successive interference cancellation (SIC)¹ in which the receiver exploits decoded packets to remove their replicas from previously unresolved and memorized collisions. SIC can also improve the throughput performance in TA with gated access [9], and the combination of SIC and K -MPR can push this performance further [10]. However, results targeting a combination of MPR and SIC in the context of TA with free access are missing and the aim of this paper is to fill this gap.

TAs with free access were less investigated than the variants with gated or windowed access (where the newly arrived users can not transmit while the collision resolution is in place), despite their protocol simplicity. We mention the work in [11], introducing a method for the derivation of the MST of TA with free access and showing that it is higher than the MST of TA with gated access [11]. A method to compute the MST in TAs with free access via the theory of multitype branching processes (MTBP) was presented in [7]. The method was also applied to the variant with SIC, showing that the MST increases.

In this paper, we study a random-access scheme that combines a binary tree algorithm (BTA) with the free access policy and with MPR and SIC capabilities implemented at the physical layer.² Its contributions are: (i) We extend the analysis presented in [7] to derive the MST in BTA with free access, where the receiver can decode up to and including K packets simultaneously (denoted by K -MPR) and also applies SIC among the last undecoded and memorized slot and the currently received slot. We consider two variants of the scheme, where in the first the receiver can execute both decoding-triggered and blind SIC, while in the second

¹We use the term SIC to denote the application of interference cancellation across slots and assume that MPR operates on individual slot basis.

²The preliminary version of this work was presented in [12].

only decoding-triggered SIC can be executed (the details are presented in Section III). (ii) We compare the performance of the scheme with other types of tree-algorithms that leverage K -MPR and/or SIC. We show that the scheme offers a favorable performance, approaching the performance of the state of the art TA while requiring simple protocol operation at the device side, making it a good candidate for the massive uncoordinated uplink access scenarios.

The rest of the text is organized as follows. Section II accounts the related work. Section III discusses the system model. Section IV presents the analysis and Section V presents the performance evaluation. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The analytical treatment of TAs with free access for infinite user population was first performed in [11], and then further explored in [7]. The authors of [11] developed the functional equation of Poisson generating function (PGF) and used the iteration method to determine the MST, which is the maximum arrival rate λ_{\max} for which a packet from an infinite user population has the finite amount of delay of successful reception with probability one.

Applicability of MTBP theory to TA with free access was demonstrated in [13]. This approach was exploited to determine the MST of TAs with free access [7]. It is based on the computation of the spectral radius of the expectation matrix \mathbf{M} , whose entries $m_{i,j}$ are the expected number of children of type j of a parent of type i . In the context of TAs, types correspond to slot degrees (more details about the \mathbf{M} matrix are presented in Section IV). The values of $m_{i,j}$, $\forall i, j$, depend on the rate of new arrivals into the system, and the MST is the value λ_{\max} for which the spectral radius of \mathbf{M} becomes 1. It was shown that the MST for BTA with free access is 0.36018 (packet/slot), while the modified TA with free access achieves 0.3932 [7]. In the case of the algorithm with a single-slot memory and SIC, the MST becomes 0.5699, which is a significant increase. The impact of K -MPR on MST in BTA was also investigated in [7]. It was observed that the MST increases with K ; for instance, when $K = 2$, the MST is 0.7624, while when $K = 10$, the MST is 4.1636.

For the sake of completeness, we also mention state of the art TA's that also leverage SIC and MPR. Specifically, the use of SIC for TA's was initially proposed in [9], showing that the throughput of the algorithm in gated access reaches 0.6931. The work in [10] analyzed the scenario that combines K -MPR and SIC, showing that the MST performance can be pushed further if windowed access is used. The results from this work will be used for comparison in Section V.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider an infinite user population contending over a time-slotted random access channel to access the common access point (AP). The arrivals in the system are Poisson-distributed with intensity λ , where each packet arrival happens at a new user. The channel time-slots are of fixed length that corresponds to the duration of a single packet. We also assume

that all packets carry information of the slot when they were transmitted for the first time, which we denote as the *pointer* in further text. The channel is considered to be error-free and the common access point is capable of K -MPR.

The AP also has a single-slot memory in which it stores the signal received in the last undecoded slot for the purpose of SIC. The SIC can be performed both in the *backward* and *forward* manner, as elaborated later. For the ease of exposition, we denote the backward and forward SIC by B-SIC and F-SIC, respectively.

The access protocol operation proceeds as follows. The newly arrived users transmit immediately at the beginning of the next slot, say slot s_i . These transmissions are concurrent with the retransmissions from a subgroup of the users that contended previously, were unsuccessful and became backlogged (if there were such). We note that the backlog queue operates as a stack i.e., in the last-in-first-out manner. We denote the group (set) of users transmitting in slot s_i by \mathcal{G}_i , their individual signals by Y_j , $j \in \mathcal{G}_i$, and the composite signal observed in s_i by S_i , where $S_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{G}_i} Y_j$. Further, we denote by $|S_i|$ the degree of slot s_i , which is number of the individual signals contained in S_i , and which is equal to size of \mathcal{G}_i , i.e., $|S_i| = |\mathcal{G}_i|$. We also point out the main collision resolution rule of the protocol, applied when $|S_i| > K$ (i.e., when signal S_i can not be decoded using K -MPR): the rule is that the users in \mathcal{G}_i split into two new (sub)groups, $\mathcal{G}_{i,1}$ and $\mathcal{G}_{i,2}$. The splitting is performed randomly and independently, where each user with probability p decides to join $\mathcal{G}_{i,1}$ and with probability $1 - p$ to join $\mathcal{G}_{i,2}$.³ Users from $\mathcal{G}_{i,1}$ transmit in the next slot, s_{i+1} , jointly with newly arrived users, while the users in $\mathcal{G}_{i,2}$ become backlogged.

Upon observing S_i , the AP attempts its decoding, which is successful if $|S_i| \leq K$. In this case, the AP retrieves all the individual signals Y_j , $j \in \mathcal{G}_i$, and learns through the pointers included in the decoded packets whether some of the decoded users transmitted previously. This way, the access point learns whether there is an intersection among \mathcal{G}_i and the group of users who transmitted in the signal currently memorized by the AP, denoted by \mathcal{G}_l and S_l , respectively, where $l < i$.⁴ If $\mathcal{G}_i \cap \mathcal{G}_l \neq \emptyset$ (i.e., the users from $\mathcal{G}_{i,1}$ retransmitted in S_l), the access point performs *type-1* B-SIC, subtracting the signals of these from S_l . In other words, the AP computes

$$S_l^{B_1} = S_l - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{G}_i \cap \mathcal{G}_l} Y_j \quad (1)$$

which effectively reduces the degree of the memorized signal, i.e., we have $|S_l^{B_1}| = |S_l| - |\mathcal{G}_i \cap \mathcal{G}_l|$. If $|S_l^{B_1}| \leq K$, then the AP can decode all the remaining transmissions in $S_{i-1}^{B_1}$, i.e., decode all the users in $\mathcal{G}_l \setminus \mathcal{G}_i$. This also means that the backlogged group at the top of the backlog stack becomes decoded. The AP clears its memory content and, in the next step, the backlogged group that is now at the top of the stack transmits jointly with the newly arrived users. This is depicted

³If $p = 1/2$, the splitting is fair.

⁴Recall that the memorized signal S_l corresponds to the last undecoded slot.

Fig. 1. An example of BTA with 2-MPR and SIC: Users A, B, C and D transmit in slot s_1 . Their collision is of degree 4 and thus undecodable, so the received signal S_1 is memorized and the users are instructed by the AP to split into two groups. A,B and D join $\mathcal{G}_{1,1}$, while C joins $\mathcal{G}_{1,2}$ and becomes backlogged. Group $\mathcal{G}_{1,1}$ retransmits in s_2 , there were no new arrivals. S_2 is also not decodable, however, using the type-2 B-SIC, the AP removes S_2 (i.e., the composite transmissions of A, B, and D) from S_1 , enabling decoding of C's packet and removing it from the backlog. Subsequently, the AP replaces the content of the memory with S_2 and instructs A, B, and D to split again: A chooses $\mathcal{G}_{2,1}$ and B, D chose $\mathcal{G}_{2,2}$ which becomes backlogged. Group $\mathcal{G}_{2,1}$ transmits in s_3 and there were no new arrivals. The slot is decoded, triggering type-2 B-SIC, after which $\mathcal{G}_{2,2}$ becomes decoded as well. In the next slot, E, F, and G transmit for the first time, the slot can not be decoded and they split, such that they all chose $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$. $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ transmits in the next slot, along with H that arrived. The AP decodes H using F-SIC, while E, F, and G split; E and G chose $\mathcal{G}_{5,1}$ and H chose $\mathcal{G}_{5,2}$. $\mathcal{G}_{5,1}$ transmits in the next slot along with newly arrived I and J. The slot is undecodable and a new split is performed, in which I chose $\mathcal{G}_{6,1}$ and E, G, and J chose $\mathcal{G}_{6,2}$. $\mathcal{G}_{6,1}$ transmits in the next slot, which gets decoded and triggers type-1 B-SIC. However, the decoding attempt of $\mathcal{G}_{6,2}$ after type-1 B-SIC was not successful, so $\mathcal{G}_{6,2}$ splits again, such that G chose $\mathcal{G}_{7,1}$ and E and J chose $\mathcal{G}_{7,2}$, while the group $\mathcal{G}_{6,2}$ gets removed from the backlog. $\mathcal{G}_{7,1}$ transmits in the next slot along with K that arrived. The slot gets decoded, triggering type-1 B-SIC after which $\mathcal{G}_{7,2}$ becomes decoded as well. In the next slot, the group that is now at the top of the backlog stack, which is $\mathcal{G}_{5,2}$ transmits in the next slot along with newly arrived users L and M.

in Fig. 1, where: (i) the decoding of user A in slot 3 triggers type-1 B-SIC, after which B and D become decoded and removed from the backlog stack, and (ii) the decoding of user G and K in slot 8 triggers type-1 B-SIC, after which E and J become decoded and removed from the backlog stack.

Otherwise, if $|S_i^{B_1}| > K$, i.e., the backlogged group at the top of the stack $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$ can not be decoded, the AP keeps $S_i^{B_1}$ in the memory, while $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$ splits into two new groups, denoted with a slight abuse of notation with $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$ and $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$. The users from $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$ retransmit in the next slot, jointly with the newly arrived users, while the users that have chosen $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$ remain backlogged at the top of the stack. This is illustrated in Fig. 1, where after the decoding of user I in slot 7 and type-1 B-SIC, the memorized signal still can not be decoded, and the group {E,G,J} splits, such that G transmits in slot 8 and {E,J} remain

backlogged.

If $|S_i| > K$, then the received signal can not be decoded. In this case, the AP first performs *type-2* B-SIC by computing

$$S_i^{B_2} = S_i - S_i. \quad (2)$$

In the case that $\mathcal{G}_i \subset \mathcal{G}_l$ (i.e., only the group $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$ of users that transmitted in s_l retransmitted in s_i and there were no new arrivals) and $|S_i^{B_2}| \leq K$, the AP will be able to decode the signals in $S_i^{B_2}$. This effectively means that the backlogged group at the top of the stack $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$ becomes isolated through type-2 B-SIC, and can be decoded and removed from the top of the stack. Also, type-2 B-SIC does not affect the content of S_i , as s_i remains undecodable, and the AP replaces the content of its memory (which currently holds S_l) with S_i . An example of this scenario is depicted in Fig. 1, where type-2

B-SIC performed after observing slot 2 enables decoding of user C. We note that the difference between type-1 and type-2 B-SIC is that type-1 B-SIC is triggered and guided by a decoding event, while type-2 B-SIC is performed blindly.

If the decoding of $S_i^{B_2}$ was not successful, the AP performs F-SIC by computing

$$S_i^F = S_i - S_l. \quad (3)$$

In the case that $\mathcal{G}_l \subset \mathcal{G}_i$ (i.e., all users that transmitted in s_l retransmitted in s_i along with some newly arrived users, also implying that $\mathcal{G}_{l,1} = \mathcal{G}_l$ and $\mathcal{G}_{l,2} = \emptyset$) and if $|S_i^F| \leq K$, the AP will be able to decode newly arrived users in s_i . This way, the remaining undecoded users in S_i are the ones from s_l , i.e., the ones in $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$. The users in $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$ split into two new groups, denoted again with a slight abuse of notation with $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$ and $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$. The users from $\mathcal{G}_{l,1}$ transmit in the next slot, $\mathcal{G}_{l,2}$ becomes backlogged, while S_l remains in the AP's memory. An example of this is depicted in Fig. 1, where F-SIC performed on slot 5 enables decoding of user H and removal of the empty group from the backlog. We also note that F-SIC is performed blindly, i.e., it is not triggered by a decoding event. Further, if F-SIC was not successful, then the content of the AP's memory is replaced with S_i , while the users in \mathcal{G}_i split into $\mathcal{G}_{i,1}$ and $\mathcal{G}_{i,2}$, such that the users in $\mathcal{G}_{i,1}$ transmit in the next slot and the ones in $\mathcal{G}_{i,2}$ become backlogged.

Finally, a slot may also be idle, which implies that there were no new arrivals and that, if the stack is non-empty, the backlogged group at the top of the stack was empty. The next backlogged group in the stack (if there is such) retransmits in the next slot, jointly with newly arrived users.

The protocol operation continues on slot-by-slot basis. To facilitate easier understanding, Fig. 1 provides an example, in which it is assumed that $K = 2$.

The complete specification of the protocol should also include definition of the feedback signals sent by the BS and actions performed after feedback reception, including the management of the state variables (i.e., counters) maintained by the contending users, according to which the users decide when to transmit. Specifically, we assume that initial state of the counter is set to 0. Whenever the value of the counter becomes 0, the user (re)transmits. Table I specifies these aspects of the protocol.

Table II shows the states of the counters of the users at the beginning of the slots corresponding to the example in Fig. 1, their contention outcomes, and feedback signals.

The performance parameter of interest in this paper is the MST (i.e., λ_{\max}), which is achieved for optimal splitting probability p_{opt} .

Variant of the algorithm without blind SIC

In the previous text, it was assumed that the AP can perform SIC blindly by subtracting signals containing more than K transmissions that have not been decoded; this is the case for both type-2 B-SIC and F-SIC. In practice, this assumption may not hold: e.g., if the retransmitted signals experience different channel conditions and synchronization offsets from

the original transmissions, the AP may be able to execute SIC that is only triggered by a decoding event, after which the content of the packet (e.g., a training sequence contained in it) can be used to estimate the channel and synchronization offsets of the replica to be removed from the memorized signal [14]. For such scenarios, we consider a variant of the algorithm in which only type-1 B-SIC is possible. In terms of the protocol operation, this version of the algorithm is simpler, as it does not involve feedback signals F4 and F5 and the corresponding actions, see Table I.

IV. ANALYSIS

To analyze the described tree algorithm, we apply the MTBP theory. A MTBP models evolution of the population of individuals classified in $d + 1$ distinct types over generations, represented by the vector $\mathbf{Z}(n) = [Z_0(n), Z_1(n), \dots, Z_d(n)]$ where $Z_i(n)$ is the number of individuals of type i , $0 \leq i \leq d$, in generation n . In each generation, a parent of type i , $0 \leq i, j \leq d$, can produce a number c_j of children of any type j , $0 \leq j \leq d$, with probability p_{i,c_0,c_1,\dots,c_d} that is independent from other parents and their types and that does not change over generations. The sequence of vectors $\mathbf{Z}(n)$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ defines a Markov chain.

In the context of tree algorithms, the slot degrees represent the types and the branching corresponds to the collision resolution procedure. Our primary interest is to derive $m_{i,j}$, which is the expected number of children slots of degree j that will be created from a parent slot of degree i . The slot degrees of the children depend on degree of the parent slot i , arrival intensity λ , and the splitting probability p . In principle, both i and j can be arbitrarily high due to the new arrivals joining the collision resolution procedure, but we limit their values to some constant d for which the probability that the slot degree of the parent/child is higher than d is negligible.⁵ Importantly, note that slots of degree up to and including K will not produce a new generation (i.e., they will have no children), as they will be immediately decoded. In the example in Fig. 1:

- parent slot 2 is of degree 3 and its child is slot 3 that is of degree 1;
- parent slot 5 is of degree 4, and it has two children that are (i) slot 6, which is of degree 3 (after type-1 B-SIC is applied), and (ii) slot 9 which is also of degree 3;
- slot 8 has no children (the same applies for slots 3 and 7).

According to the MTBP theory, if the spectral radius of the matrix $\mathbf{M} = [m_{i,j}]$, $K \leq i, j \leq d$ (the matrix entries are the expected number of type j children from a parent of type i), is less or equal to 1 (\mathbf{M} should also be non-negative and irreducible), then the MPT is (sub-)critical and will become extinct in a finite amount of generations with probability 1. This translates into finite delay of collision resolution in the context of tree algorithms, which implies that the algorithm is stable for the given arrival intensity.

⁵The work in [7] suggests $d \leq 20$. In this paper, we consider $d = 70$.

TABLE I
SPECIFICATION OF THE FEEDBACK SIGNALS OF THE AP AND THE ACTIONS PERFORMED BY THE USERS.

2*outcome	feedback signal	1 st transmission	action after retransmission	being backlogged
O1: both S_i and S_l decoded	F1	decoded, stop transmitting	decoded, stop transmitting	decrease C by 2
O2: S_i decoded and it contained no retransmissions	F2	decoded, stop transmitting	/	decrease C by 1; if $C = 0$, transmit in the next slot
O3: S_i decoded, decoding of S_l failed	F3	decoded, stop transmitting	decoded, stop transmitting	if $C = 1$ split, if joined group 1 decrease C by 1
O4: S_i^F decoded	F4	decoded, stop transmitting	split, if joined group 2, increase C by 1	/
O5: S_l^{B2} decoded, decoding of S_i failed	F5	split, if joined group 2, increase C by 1	split, if joined group 2, increase C by 1	if decoded, stop transmitting, else, decrease C by 2
O6: no decoding was possible	F6	split, if joined group 2, increase C by 1	split, if joined group 2, increase C by 1	increase C by 1
O7: the current slot was idle	F7	/	/	decrease C by 1; if $C = 0$, transmit in the next slot

TABLE II
STATES OF THE USERS' COUNTERS AT THE BEGINNING OF THE SLOTS FOR THE EXAMPLE IN FIG. 1, CONTENTION OUTCOMES AND FEEDBACK SIGNALS. "*" DENOTES THAT THE USER IS RESOLVED, WHILE "-" DENOTES THAT THE USER HAS NOT TRANSMITTED YET.

2*slot	users' counters at the start of the slot													2*outcome	feedback signal
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M		
s_1	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	O6	F6
s_2	0	0	*	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	O5	F5
s_3	0	*	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	O1	F1
s_4	*	*	*	*	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	O6	F6
s_5	*	*	*	*	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	O4	F4
s_6	*	*	*	*	0	1	0	*	0	0	-	-	-	O6	F6
s_7	*	*	*	*	1	2	1	*	0	1	-	-	-	O3	F3
s_8	*	*	*	*	1	2	1	*	*	0	0	-	-	O1	F1
s_9	*	*	*	*	*	0	*	*	*	*	*	0	0	O6	F6

In order to derive \mathbf{M} we leverage the method presented in [7]. Recall that users contending in a slot, say s_n , with $|S_n| > K$, will end up in an undecodable slot. The users then split into groups $G_{n,1}$ and $G_{n,2}$. The expected number of groups of size j after slot of degree i gets split is

$$b_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \binom{i}{j} (p^j (1-p)^{i-j} + p^{i-j} (1-p)^j) & i > K, 0 \leq j \leq i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

where the first summand corresponds to $G_{n,1}$ and the second to $G_{n,2}$. We introduce matrix $\mathbf{B} = [b_{i,j}]$ of order $d+1$.

Now we introduce square matrix $\mathbf{H} = [h_{i,j}]$ of order $d+1$ whose entries correspond to the expected number of groups $G_{n,2}$ of size j after collision of degree i is split and which will not retransmit after SIC is applied, either because they are decoded (if $G_{n,1} \leq K$), or they perform immediate split

(if $G_{n,1} > K$). The elements of \mathbf{H} are given by

$$h_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \binom{i}{j} p^{i-j} (1-p)^j \sum_{k=0}^{K-i+j} l_k & i > K, 0 \leq i-j \leq K \\ \binom{i}{j} p^{i-j} (1-p)^j l_0 & i > K+1, \\ 1 \leq j \leq \min(K, i-K-1) & \\ p^i \sum_{k=0}^K l_k & i > K, j=0. \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where

$$l_k = \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} e^{-\lambda}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5)$$

is the probability that k new users arrived in a slot. The first case in (4) corresponds to the scenario in which the size of first group is $|G_{n,1}| = i-j$ combined with the number of newly arrived users k is such that $i-j+k \leq K$, enabling decoding of the $G_{n,1}$, application of type-2 B-SIC and the decoding or the immediate split of $G_{n,2}$. The second case (4) refers to the scenario in which there were no new arrivals, and the number

of users in $G_{n,2}$ is up to K , such that type-1 B-SIC is applied and the users in $G_{n,2}$ were immediately decoded. Finally, the third case in (4) corresponds to the scenario in which all users choose $G_{n,1}$ and there were up to and including K new arrivals, which were decoded after F-SIC was applied. This way the AP learned that $G_{n,2}$ is empty, and the corresponding slot can be skipped. As the result, the total expected number of the groups with j users that will retransmit after a slot of degree is i gets split can be written in the matrix $\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{H}$.

However, the children slots include both retransmissions and potential new arrivals and their degrees are the sums of the sizes of the retransmitting groups and the number of newly transmitting users. It can be verified that the expected number of children slots of degree j of a parent slot of degree i , $0 \leq i, j \leq d$, after type-1 B-SIC is applied and after new arrivals are taken into account can be written down in the matrix $(\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{H})\mathbf{L}$, where \mathbf{L} is a square matrix of order $d + 1$

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} l_0 & l_1 & l_2 & l_3 & l_4 & \dots & \sum_{k=d}^{\infty} l_k \\ & l_0 & l_1 & l_2 & l_3 & \dots & \sum_{k=d-1}^{\infty} l_k \\ & & l_0 & l_1 & l_2 & \dots & \sum_{k=d-2}^{\infty} l_k \\ & & & l_0 & l_1 & \dots & \sum_{k=d-3}^{\infty} l_k \\ & & & & l_0 & \dots & \sum_{k=d-4}^{\infty} l_k \\ & & & & & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & & & & & \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} l_k = 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where l_k is given by (5).

In the next step, we introduce a square matrix $\mathbf{R} = [r_{i,j}]$ of order $d + 1$ whose entries correspond to the expected number of children slots whose degree will be changed as a result of F-SIC

$$r_{i,j} = \begin{cases} -p^i l_k & i = j - k > K, k = 1, \dots, K \\ p^i \sum_{k=0}^K l_k & i = j > K \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The first case corresponds to the scenario in which the child slot of degree j was produced by all the users from the parent slot of degree i (they all choose the first group) and $1 \leq k \leq K$ new arrivals. These new arrivals were removed by F-SIC, reducing the degree of the child slot back to i . The second case accounts for these children slots whose degree was reduced to i . As the result, after F-SIC is applied, the expected number of degree j children of the parent degree i slot can be written down in the matrix $(\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{H})\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{R}$.

Thus, combining the derived expressions, the expectation matrix \mathbf{M} can be constructed as (analogously to what was exposed in [7])

$$\mathbf{M} = (\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{H})\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{R}. \quad (7)$$

Finally, we note that the parent slot of degree $i \leq K$ does not generate any children, as well as that the children of degree $j \leq K$ are immediately decoded. Therefore, we remove the first $K + 1$ rows and $K + 1$ columns from \mathbf{M} (corresponding to $0 \leq i, j \leq K$) and compute the the spectral radius of the

resulting matrix, with a slight abuse of notation also denoted by \mathbf{M} .

It can be shown that \mathbf{M} is a positive and irreducible matrix. Thus, its dominant eigenvalue is positive and equal to its spectral radius $\rho(\mathbf{M})$, where $\rho(\mathbf{M})$ depends on the splitting probability p and the arrival intensity λ . As already indicated, in order for the algorithm to be stable, the following condition has to be satisfied

$$\rho(\mathbf{M}) \leq 1. \quad (8)$$

The MST of the algorithm is equal to the maximum arrival intensity λ_{\max} that can be attained for some optimal splitting probability p_{opt} for which $\rho(\mathbf{M}) \leq 1$. Formally, we write

$$\mathbf{max.} \lambda \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{s.t.} \rho(\mathbf{M}) \leq 1 \quad (10)$$

$$0 < p < 1 \quad (11)$$

$$0 < \lambda < K \quad (12)$$

where the last constraint follows from the simple fact that λ can not be higher than K , as this is the maximum number of concurrently transmitting users that the AP can resolve using K -MPR. In the next section, we solve this optimization problem with a simple grid search over the allowed range values of p and λ .

MST the variant without blind SIC

The derivation of the MST for this variant of the algorithm can be done in a straightforward way, by removing the entries of the matrix \mathbf{H} that correspond to type-2 B-SIC and F-SIC. Specifically, we have

$$h_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \binom{i}{j} p^{i-j} (1-p)^j \sum_{k=0}^{K-i+j} l_k & i > K, 0 \leq i-j \leq K \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

We can compute \mathbf{M} from the following expression

$$\mathbf{M} = (\mathbf{B} - \mathbf{H})\mathbf{L} \quad (14)$$

where, in comparison to (7), we removed matrix \mathbf{R} from the equation to get (14), since \mathbf{R} is also related to application of F-SIC and the consequential change of the degrees of the children. Finally, the computation of the MST proceeds analogously as in the previous case.

V. EVALUATION

In this section we evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm based on the analysis presented in the previous section.

Fig. 2 shows the values of the arrival intensity λ for which the spectral radius of \mathbf{M} is 1, as a function of the splitting probability p and for different values of K . Clearly, the maxima of the curves, which correspond to the MST (i.e., λ_{\max}), increase with K , and the maxima are achieved for progressively smaller values of p . The differences between the

curves for the original algorithm and the one without blind SIC are small, only becoming tangible as p increases.

Closer insights in the behaviour of the MST λ_{\max} and the optimal splitting probability p_{opt} can be obtained from Table ???. Obviously, the p_{opt} decreases as K grows, implying that the accommodation of a larger intensity of new arrivals as K grows comes at the expense of “biasing” the undecoded users to choose the second group more often, and thus to refrain from retransmitting. The Table ??? also shows the results for the MST normalized with K , which can be used as a fair comparison measure if the K -MPR capability requires a K -time increase of the slot size (i.e., a K -time increase of the time-frequency resources contained in a slot), which is the case for some physical layer techniques [15], [16]. Evidently, the normalized MST slightly decreases at first, and then starts to steadily increase. Similar observations can be made for the variant of the algorithm without blind SIC: the achievable MST’s in this case are somewhat lower than for the original variant of the algorithm, and the difference decreases as K increases, being more tangible for low values of K . The values of the optimal splitting probability p_{opt} in this case are also lower than the ones corresponding to the original variant of the algorithm; this is the consequence of the fact that this variant can not “isolate” and decode new arrivals in case that the splitting was such that all the users that split have chosen the first group and retransmitted together (see Section III), and thus the users are more biased not to choose the first group.

Further, the table also reproduces the results from [7] for the MST when only K -MPR is used. It is obvious that use of SIC in our scheme, although limited to just the last received undecoded slot at a time, significantly increases the MST performance.

Finally, the table also compares the MST of the proposed scheme with the MST of the tree-algorithm that uses windowed access, K -MPR, SIC, and can memorize all previously undecoded slots for the purpose of SIC [10]. Obviously, the latter scheme has a superior performance, however it comes at the expense of a more complex operation of the access protocol, as well as the potentially unlimited memory requirements. Further, it is easy to show that the relative difference between in the MST performance of the two algorithms decreases with K .

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we assessed a combination MPR with SIC in binary tree algorithm with free access. Our results show that such scheme offers improvement in the maximum stable throughput performance in comparison to the binary tree algorithm with free access that exploit only MPR or SIC with the single-slot memory. Moreover, the performance of the algorithm tends to the one with MPR, SIC, unlimited memory and windowed access, which is the best performing BTA algorithm in the so far available literature. Finally, we also showed that the gain of using “blind” SIC diminishes as K grows.

Fig. 2. Arrival intensity λ for which the spectral radius of \mathbf{M} becomes 1 as function of splitting probability p .

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Ali M. Syed for implementing part of the evaluations in MATLAB.

This paper has received funding in part from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 856967 and in part from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 101086387.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. Liberg, M. Sundberg, E. Wang, J. Bergman, J. Sachs, Cellular Internet of things: technologies, standards, and performance, Academic Press, 2017.
- [2] 3GPP, TS36.321 - Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol specification., Tech. rep. (Dec. 2020).
- [3] P. Masek, D. Hudec, J. Krejci, A. Ometov, J. Hosek, K. Samouylov, Communication capabilities of wireless m-bus: Remote metering within smartgrid infrastructure, in: V. M. Vishnevskiy, D. V. Kozyrev (Eds.), Distributed Computer and Communication Networks, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018, pp. 31–42.
- [4] A. Laya, L. Alonso, J. Alonso-Zarate, Is the random access channel of lte and lte-a suitable for m2m communications? a survey of alternatives, IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials 16 (1) (2013) 4–16.
- [5] R. Rom, M. Sidi, Multiple Access Protocols, Springer, 1990.
- [6] B. S. Tsybakov, V. A. Mikhailov, N. Likhanov, Bounds for packet transmission rate in a random-multiple-access system, Problemy Peredachi Informatsii 19 (1) (1983) 61–81.
- [7] G. T. Peeters, B. Van Houdt, On the Maximum Stable Throughput of Tree Algorithms With Free Access, IEEE Trans. Info. Theory 55 (11) (2009) 5087–5099.
- [8] C. Stefanovic, H. M. Gürsu, Y. Deshpande, W. Kellerer, Analysis of Tree-Algorithms with Multi-Packet Reception, in: Proc. IEEE GLOBE-COM 2020, Taipei, Taiwan, 2020.
- [9] Y. Yu, G. B. Giannakis, High-Throughput Random Access Using Successive Interference Cancellation in a Tree Algorithm, IEEE Trans. Info. Theory 53 (12) (2007) 4628–4639.
- [10] C. Stefanovic, Y. Deshpande, H. M. Gürsu, W. Kellerer, Tree-algorithms with multi-packet reception and successive interference cancellation, IEEE Transactions on Communications 71 (11) (2023) 6287–6300.
- [11] P. Mathys, P. Flajolet, Q-ary Collision Resolution Algorithms in Random-Access Systems with Free or Blocked Channel Access, IEEE Trans. Info. Theory 31 (2) (1985) 217–243.

- [12] S. M. Ali, M. Beko, D. Vukobratovic, C. Stefanovic, On the performance of the free-access tree algorithm with mpr, sic, and single-slot memory, in: 2023 International Balkan Conference on Communications and Networking (BalkanCom), 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [13] H. Mohamed, P. Robert, Dynamic tree algorithms, *The Annals of Applied Probability* 20 (1) (2010) 26–51.
URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25662549>
- [14] G. Liva, Graph-Based Analysis and Optimization of Contention Resolution Diversity Slotted ALOHA, *IEEE Trans. Commun.* 59 (2) (2011) 477–487.
- [15] D. Danyev, B. Laczay, M. Ruzinko, Multiple Access Adder Channel, in: E. Biglieri, L. Gyorfı (Eds.), *Multiple Access Channels*, IOS press, 2007, pp. 26–53.
- [16] A. Mengali, R. De Gaudenzi, P. Arapoglou, Enhancing the Physical Layer of Contention Resolution Diversity Slotted ALOHA, *IEEE Trans. Commun.* 65 (10) (2017) 4295–4308.